

RELATIONSHIP OF SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECOND-YEAR TEACHER EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to determine if there is a relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement among second year BEED students at UM Peñaplata College. This particular study has used the quantitative–descriptive correlational design to determine the level of self-directed learning in terms of learning motivation, planning and implementing, self-monitoring, and interpersonal communication to academic achievement. The researchers utilized an adapted questionnaire for the Self-Directed Learning and used a secondary data for the academic achievement of students. The statistical tools used in the study were the Mean and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (Pearson r). The result shows that among the second year BEED students the level of self-directed learning is at high level which means that self-directed learning is manifested most of the time. The students' level of academic achievement is B+ Distinction means that the students are performing well and able to understand the lesson well. Moreover, there was no significant relationship between students' level of self-directed learning and level of academic achievement; it is understandable that the increase and decrease of level of self-directed learning doesn't affect the level of academic achievement. The study confirmed that there is no significant relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement. Therefore, further study is required to clearly understand the other mechanisms between these two variables.

Keywords: self-directed learning, academic achievement, students, correlational research, Bachelor of Elementary Education, UM Peñaplata College.

I. INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement is one of the most essential measures of educational progress, and it is the only aim that the entire educational system must strive for. In other words, society is concerned about the fate of the individual, his successful development and status in the community, and expects to excel in a variety of areas, including cognitive skills and abilities, personality development, emotional and behavioral development, and excellence (Tabbodi et al., 2015).

African Americans have long been subjected to academic inequalities. To say that these historical injustices have ongoing consequences in the twenty-first century is an understatement. As a result, some African Americans remain dissatisfied with and distrustful of their nation's educational system, the African American male population continues to trail behind the rest (Adams-King, 2016). The main reasons for the poor academic performance of college students are the lack of lofty ambitions, and specific goals, the existence of cognitive misunderstandings and loose emotions, the distortion of life values, the defects of personality and ability, etc.; the objective reasons comes from many aspects such as the family, school, and social environment (Wu & Xin, 2019).

The Philippines has continuously done poorly, both in international examinations such as the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and in our own National Achievement Tests (Torio, 2016). In 2003, the Philippines placed 34th out of 38 nations in High School Math and 43rd out of 46 countries in High School Science; in 2008, we placed 10th out of ten countries in the TIMSS Advanced. Moreover, in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), in reading comprehension, the Philippines ranks last out of 79 countries, and in mathematics and science, it ranks in the low 70s. There is no denying that the country is now performing poorly and having the higher chances to have low achievements in academic. Many studies in Mindanao have discovered that first-year college students have a high probability of poor academic performance. These students frequently struggle with the transition to higher education and have variable degrees of adjustment to college during their first year, which predicts their academic achievement (Credé & Niehorster, 2012). Several factors like students' effort, previous schooling, parent's educational background, family income, self-motivation of students, age of the student, learning preferences, and entry qualifications affect the academic performance students' academic performance in a different setting (Agas et al., 2019). Thus, students must take initiative in order to flourish in their new environment consequently; there is some evidence that kids may need to be prepared for self-directed learning in order to be academically successful (Perry et al., 2001).

In UM Peñaplata College (UMPC) self-directed learning (SDL) was observed particularly in the second year students of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) Program, which is a big challenge for them to excel in academic as well as a tendency to have low grades. This prompted the researchers to conduct this study. The goal of this study is to determine if there is a relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement among second year BEED students at UM Peñaplata College.

A. Statement of the Problem

In line with the purpose, this study aims to determine the relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement among second year BEED students in UM Peñaplata College.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of self-directed learning among students in terms of:
 - 1.1 learning motivation;
 - 1.2 planning and implementing;
 - 1.3 self-monitoring; and
 - 1.4 interpersonal communication?
2. What is the level of academic achievement among students in terms of their general weighted average?
3. Is there a significant relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement among students?

B. Hypothesis

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement among students.

C. Review of Related Literature

Self-Directed Learning

Self-directed learning is a critical ability in 21st-century education. Learning motivation, planning and implementing, self monitoring, and even intelligence are all capable of self-directed learning. However, the degree of development varies due to individual differences, including learning motivation, planning and implementing, self monitoring, and even intelligence. Because information is now available from a variety of sources, the methods for getting and utilizing it have changed dramatically in recent years. As a result, the assumption that information is unchanging, as well as the belief that authorities have absolute and correct information, has been questioned.

Self-directed learning (SDL) has been identified as a learning strategy that has gotten a lot of attention in recent years, especially in higher education. According to Shen et al., (2014) self-directed learning has been linked to enhanced curiosity, critical thinking, understanding quality, retention and recall, better decision making, achievement satisfaction, motivation, competence, and confidence.

Adult education is where the concept of self-directed learning came from stated by Roberson (2005). On the other hand, self-directed learning has been utilized as coursed distance learning. Some studies discovered a link between self-directed learning and academic success in the typical classroom setting in this case. Self-directed learning is also a major predictor of academic accomplishment in non-web-based distant learning nevertheless, as what Hsu and Shiue (2005) stated.

Furthermore, Karatas and Basbay (2014) and Tekkol and Demirel (2018) stated that, the growth of information and communication technology and the expansion in virtual learning options has led to a change in people's understanding of learning. The only source of information, according to old thinking, was the teacher. Information sources have gotten increasingly diversified in recent years. As knowledge has become more accessible, the nature of learning has changed as well. It used to be vital to recall information, but nowadays it's more important to learn how to obtain information and how to learn it.

Basically, people are required to learn how to learn. Individuals who are unable to learn how to learn and arrange their own learning processes are at a disadvantage in many areas of today's globalizing world, where technology is fast evolving (Taskin, 2019). We come across the concept of 'self-directed learning' at this point, which refers to the necessity for people to govern their own learning processes. Learners who are self-directed establish plans by deciding on their learning objectives. They organize the methods for gaining access to educational materials. They're also curious, autonomous, and willing to learn on their own time (du Toit-Brits & Van Zyl, 2017).

In addition, according to Agum et al., (2021), in new normal setting self-directed learning is encouraged in the Philippines by fostering a student-centered learning environment. Hence, learners achieve self-regulated learning in basic education, which includes pre-school, elementary, and high school, where they learn to study at their own pace while adhering to the guidelines provided by their teachers. College students, on the other hand, acquire SDL by studying at their own pace, following their own guidelines, and receiving less assistance from lecturers as long as they do the tasks that have been set to them. They often go above and above what is expected of them at school.

Academic Achievement

Academic success is regarded as one of the most essential and traditional indicators of a student's development in science education. Higher achievement is valued in society as an indicator of higher chances of getting high-status occupations and higher ability to pursue higher education (Okoye & Okecha, 2008). This is not only because higher achievement indicates higher technical skills, which are currently in short supply, but also because higher achievement is valued in society as an indicator of higher chances of getting high-status occupations and higher ability to pursue higher education.

Motivation and academic emotions influenced self-regulated learning practices greatly (Zheng 2016). Academic achievement was positively influenced by self-regulated learning practices. Furthermore, through the mediating influence of self-regulated learning mechanisms, motivation and academic mood had a significant impact on academic accomplishment.

Meanwhile, when schools combine efforts to improve children's intellectual, social, and emotional learning, they will be more effective in their educational objective. Children's academic success and lifetime learning are both aided by social and emotional learning. According to Cristóvo et al., (2017), researchers have established that social and emotional learning not only influences nonacademic outcomes, but also plays a key role in boosting children's academic performance and lifetime learning.

According to Dagnev (2015), academic achievement is defined as students' performance in the subjects they learn in school, implying that academic achievement influences the student's standing in the class. It allows students to hone their skills, enhance their grades, and prepare for future academic difficulties. It is standard practice to move pupils from one class to another based on their academic performance.

In addition, based from Muhammad and Aziz (2019), academic achievement refers to a student's performance in fulfilling short- or long-term educational goals. Academic achievement may also refer to a person's outstanding success in a particular academic field. Academic accomplishment is the extent to which students, instructors, and institutes have met their objectives (outcomes). It is a multidimensional concept that is concerned with the potential and performance of pupils. Academic success is influenced by cognitive, emotional, physical, and social variables. It refers to students' lives as a whole, from elementary school through their professional careers.

According to Blandin (2016), the nation can no longer overlook the poor academic achievement of kids from different racial/ethnic and socioeconomic backgrounds. The negative consequences of such underachievement reach beyond the educational system, threatening the social, moral, and economic foundation of society itself. On the other hand, a large amount of research has been conducted on the influence of frequent exams on student achievement. Most of these studies have found that increasing the frequency of tests leads to higher academic success (Kulik and Kulik 1987), as cited by Sulun et al., (2018).

The impact of frequent exams and quizzes on scientific teaching and learning has been studied at many educational levels ranging from elementary schools to universities. This technique has the potential to benefit students by detecting mistakes early and boosting and sustaining high levels of learning achievement. Quizzes and assignments, as teaching aids, may offer students with relevant feedback and error correction throughout educational courses. The quiz is a useful tool for motivating and assessing pupils' progress, especially when taken often. It may also have positive benefits such as increasing academic success, decreasing anxiety, enhancing student-professor communication, and shortening the time required to study for the final test (Zamini et al. 2013).

Another key advantage of testing is that it provides positive motivation for students; because they want to do well in the course, they study hard and devote significant time to preparing for quizzes. Another viewpoint is that strong quiz results assist students in achieving academic success. As previously stated, this has a positive effect in that students prepare more for quizzes because the exam is a powerful motivator (Gholami & Mostafa, 2013).

According to Oluwafemi (2019), results indicated that students taught business studies utilizing programmed instruction, questioning, and assignment teaching techniques performed better with higher post-test scores than those taught using traditional teaching methods. Students taught utilizing the assignment technique outperformed those taught using programmed instruction and questioning methods in terms of post-test results. According to the study's findings, the three teaching approaches have the potential to increase students' academic achievement in Business Studies.

Significance Relationship of Self-Directed Learning and Academic Achievement

In the recent study conducted by Lew (2017) entitled The Relationship among Self-directed learning ability, Academic Self-efficacy, and Academic Achievement of Elementary School pupil. The result shown that, there were strong relationships between self-directed learning capacity, academic self-efficacy, and academic accomplishment. These findings suggest that in order to improve students' academic accomplishment, approaches to increase academic efficacy and self-directed learning capacity are needed in the field of education.

On the other hand, Kan'an and Osman (2015) examined the relationship of Self-directed Learning Readiness (SDLR) and Science Academic Achievement among 10th and 11th grade students they found that. There is a considerable link between SDLR and scientific academic accomplishment, and SDLR predicts science academic achievement significantly, with no significant changes in SDLR amongst races, nationalities, or ages. As a result, SDLR has been proposed as one of the characteristics that contribute to higher academic accomplishment in science. As well as, including SDL components into teaching and encouraging students to develop SDL abilities may be advantageous and rewarding for students' academic performance in not only science disciplines, but also other topics, as well as success in the corporate world.

Although, the outcomes of studies on the association between SDL and academic achievement have been mixed since Gebru et al., (2015) cited that there is no link between academic accomplishment and learning style, and older students are more self-directed than their young adult equivalents. Nevertheless, according to Ahmad et al. (2019), SDL had no significant link with academic achievement among Malaysian and Turkish undergraduates who participated in their study. This emphasizes the need of achieving a high SDL. It can be argued that the majority of the study participants are not very self-directed, and that a few contributing variables, one of which is a cultural component, may be to blame for the low scores.

Theoretical Framework

This study was based in Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory of a student's persistence and motivation to create success. His self-efficacy theory was based on his social learning theory, especially the intrinsic reinforcement component, which leveraged a student's own, personal qualities for success in a learning setting. In addition, he noted that in order to be effective in educational settings, pupil "must have the ability to manage their own motivation and learning activities.

This was also anchored in the Knowles adult learning theory (1984) which mentioned the five (5) Assumptions of Adult Learners. The first assumption is when a person evolves, his or her self-concept shifts from that of a dependent personality to that of a self-directed human being. Second, as a person grows older, he or she collects a larger reservoir of experience, which becomes a greater resource for learning. Third, as a person grows older, his or her readiness to learn becomes increasingly geared to the developmental tasks of his or her social roles. Fourth, as a person matures, his or her temporal perspective evolves from one of postponed application of information to one of immediacy of application, and his or her orientation toward learning shifts from subject-centeredness to problem-centeredness. The last one is learning motivation, which becomes internal as a person grows older.

Further it was supported by Brockett and Hiemstra (2018) by stating that self-direction in learning is a way of life. It isn't only a passing fad that coincides with the recent emphasis on self-development and self-help. It's also not the latest in a long line of adult education trends that will fade away in a few years. Self-education, or accepting responsibility for one's own learning, has a long history, and the current popularity of self-directed learning, in our opinion, reflects the adult education field's purposeful attempt to embrace these ideas and incorporate them into mainstream practice.

However, Candy (1991) claimed that the phrase "self-direction" is deceptive because the person should not be judged separately from the group. Learning, in his opinion, is not a solo activity but rather entails social interactions. Learning strategies can also be modeled using the SDL model. The way pupils process subject content is referred to as learning techniques. There is a distinction drawn between deep and superficial processing. The goal of deep-level processing is to find meaning in the subject matter, whereas the initial priority in surface learning is to reproduce the information.

II. METHOD

A. Research Design

The descriptive correlational research design was used in this study. Descriptive research is frequently used as a prelude to quantitative research designs, providing a basic overview and some useful clues as to which variables should be tested quantitatively (Shuttleworth, 2008). Correlational research is a good method for determining the strength of a link between two variables (Akinlua & Haan, 2019). This study were conducted by gathering data from the respondents through online survey questionnaires which identify the relationship of self-directed learning and academic achievement of second year BEED students in UM Peñaplata College that served as our primary instruments and collecting the data from this study.

B. Research Respondents

The respondents of the study are the officially enrolled second year BEED students for the first semester in UM Peñaplata College in the Island Garden City of Samal. UMPC has a total number of 42 currently enrolled second year students of BEED Department as of A.Y 2021-2022. The researchers surveyed 38 second year BEED students of UMPC to get a more reliable response to the study. The researchers used the Raosoft sample size online calculator in identifying the sample size in selecting a sample from the total population.

C. Research Instruments

Survey questionnaire was the principal instrument for the data gathering. A primary research instrument in the survey which is composed of a set of questions for all research is called a questionnaire. The researchers adapted a questionnaire that were developed by Shen (2014) to determined the level and influence of self-directed learning to the academic achievement of the second year BEED students in UMPC. The SDL questionnaire is 20 items survey with responses of five-point Likert scale: 1=Strongly Disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neutral; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly Agree. The questionnaire were printed and posted online as a tool to assessed the respondents of their personal data and information that help the researchers to determine relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement of second year BEED students in UMPC. Likert scale was used whereby respondents are asked to rate the level of the variables towards the statements stipulated in the survey questionnaire.

To measure the academic achievement of students, it utilized the institutional grading scale. The scale 96 – 100, has a grade conversion of 4.0 with a grade description of *High Distinction (A)*. If the grade description is *Distinction (B+)*, it has a grade conversion of 3.5 within the scale 90 - 95. On the other hand, if the grade conversion is 3.0 it is in the scale 85 - 89 with a

grade description of *Very Good (B-)*. However, if the grade description is *Good (C+)*, it is within the scale 80 - 84 with a grade description of 2.5. The scale of 75 -79 has a grade conversion of 2.0 with a grade description of *Average (C-)*. Lastly, if the grade is below 75, it means *Fail (F)* with a grade conversion of 1.0 (Student Handbook, 2021).

D. Research Procedure

The following procedures were observed in the gathering of data.

1. **Asking Permission to Conduct the Study.** The researchers wrote a letter asking permission from Mr. Alberto M. Condes, the director of UM Peñaplata College.
2. **Adaptation of Questionnaire.** The researchers adapted a questionnaire that were developed by Shen (2014) served as a guide in identifying the relationship of self-directed learning and academic achievement of second year BEED students in UMPC.
3. **Validation of the Questionnaires.** The researchers presented the questionnaires to the panel of examiners for the validation and approval of the questionnaires.
4. **Asking permission from the Respondent.** The researchers were formally ask the qualified respondents through sending message in their respective messenger account if they are willing to answer the survey questionnaire.
5. **Conduct the Survey.** The researchers distributed the survey questionnaires through sending them individually in their messenger account to answer the questions through Google form.
6. **Retrieval of the Survey Questionnaires.** After the survey conducted, the researchers retrieved the files from Google forms done by the researcher.
7. **Tabulation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data.** The data gathered presented in the forms of tables, graphs and/or figures with textual explanation. These data used to interpret and analyze using different applicable statistical tools.

E. Statistical Treatment of Data

The data obtained by the researchers were tabulated, measured and analyzed. Similarly, these statistical tools help the researchers established a more concrete, precise and justifiable explanations of the data obtained thereby improving the precision and validity of the statements.

Mean. This was used to measure the level of self-directed learning to the academic achievement of the respondents.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (Pearson r). This was used to measure the relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement of the students.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Level of Self-Directed Learning

Shown in Table 1 is the level of self-directed learning among second year BEED students in UMPC. Data reveals that the overall mean score is 3.96 with a .59 standard deviation. The mean score is described as *high* and shows that self-directed learning is manifested most of the time.

Table 1: Level of Self-Directed Learning

Indicators	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Descriptive Level
Learning Motivation	4.21	.49	Very High
Planning and Implementing	3.90	.69	High
Self-Monitoring	3.87	.66	High
Interpersonal Communication	3.84	.63	High
Overall Mean	3.96	.59	High

Note: N = 38, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Looking at the data for each indicator, it showed that *Learning Motivation* got the highest mean rating of 4.21 and a standard deviation of .49 with a descriptive level of very High; followed by *Planning and Implementing* with a mean rating of 3.90 or *high* with a standard deviation of .69; and *Self-monitoring*, with a mean rating of 3.87 or *high* with a standard deviation of .66. The indicator, *Interpersonal Communication*, got the lowest mean rating of 3.84 or *high* with a standard deviation of .63.

Based on the results mentioned above, the overall level of self-directed learning among second year BEED students is high. This was the answers given by the respondents in the questionnaire. In fact, among the four indicators of self-directed learning: *learning motivation, planning and implementing, self-monitoring, and interpersonal communication*, only the *learning motivation* got a very high rating, and rest of the indicators have a high rating. This means that the self-directed learning is manifested most of the time among second year BEED students in UMPC. It can be construed that the use of suitable learning strategies and resources to effectively attain learning goals (planning and implementing), examine one's own learning process and outcomes (self-monitoring), and their ability to connect with others to promote their own learning (interpersonal communication) was manifested most of the time. Thus, it is parallel to the study of Cheng et al. (2010) as cited by Van Rensburg, (2015) that identifying learning needs, formulating learning goals, identifying human and material resources for learning, and selecting and implementing appropriate learning strategies, as well as acknowledging students' willingness and openness to openly communicate their concerns about the program and regard feedback as constructive and guiding criticism were manifested most of the time in diagnosing self-directed learning.

Meanwhile, it is notable that the learning motivation got the very high mean rating which means it was manifested all the time. It can be construed that doing self-directed learning, learning motivation is essential and regardless of the results or effectiveness of learning, the respondents are still like to learn. Thus, it is parallel to the study of Guiffrida et al. (2013) stated that when students have a sense of autonomy, competence, relatedness, or purpose, they become organically motivated to learn.

B. Level of Academic Achievement

Table 2 shows the level of academic achievement among second year BEED students in UMPC measured by grades which interpreted as general weighted average (GWA). The table reveals the overall mean score of general weighted average which is 3.11 with a standard deviation of .35. The mean score is described as B+ Distinction. This indicates that the respondents' intellectual ability is above average.

Table 2: Level of Academic Achievement

Indicators	M	SD	Descriptive Level
General Weighted Average	3.11	.35	B+ Distinction

Note: N = 38, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Further, according to Okoye and Okecha, (2008) higher achievement is valued in society as an indicator of higher chances of getting high-status occupations and higher ability to pursue higher education. In addition, based from Dagnew (2015), academic achievement is defined as students' performance in the subjects they learn in school, implying that academic achievement influences the student's standing in the class. It allows students to hone their skills, enhance their grades, and prepare for future academic difficulties. It is standard practice to move pupils from one class to another based on their academic performance.

C. Significant Relationship between Self-Directed Learning and Academic Achievement of the Students

The significant relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement among second year BEED students in UMPC is reflected in table 3. The data reveal the overall computed *r*-value of -.064 with a *p*-value of .705. The confidence level set for this study was *p*<0.05. It could conclude that there is no significant relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement among second year BEED students in UMPC. The probability value was much higher than 0.05 level of significance; hence the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Self-Directed Learning and Academic Achievement of the Students

Self-Directed Learning	Academic Achievement	
	General Weighted Average	
	r-value	p-value
Learning Motivation	-.149	.371
Planning and Implementing	.017	.921
Self-Monitoring	-.093	.578
Interpersonal Communication	-.041	.806
Overall	-.064	.705

$p^* < .05$

Consequently, a close examination of the data further revealed that the indicator learning motivation of self directed learning has a r-value of -.149 with p-value of .371. As for the planning and implementing among the indicator of self-directed learning, the r-value is .017 with p-value of .921. Meanwhile, the indicator self-monitoring of self-directed learning has a r-value of -.093 with p-value of .578. As for the interpersonal communication, the r-value is -.041 with p-value of .806. It can be construed that the increase and decrease of level of self-directed learning doesn't affect the level of academic achievement. Therefore, the results reveal that while SDL has no direct effect on academic achievement, but it does provide among second year BEED students access to a variety of abilities and skills that they may utilize to become greater learners.

The above result is parallel to the study of Ahmad et al. (2019); SDL had no significant link with academic achievement among Malaysian and Turkish undergraduates who participated in their study. This emphasizes the need of achieving a high SDL. It can be argued that the majority of the study participants are not very self-directed, and that a few contributing variables, one of which is a cultural component, may be to blame for the low scores.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Among the second year BEED students the level of self-directed learning is at high level which means that self-directed learning is manifested most of the time. It can be construed that the use of suitable learning strategies and resources to effectively attain learning goals, examine one's own learning process and outcomes, and their ability to connect with others to promote their own learning was manifested most of the time. Meanwhile among the four indicators learning motivation got the very high mean rating which means it was manifested all the time. It can be construed that doing self-directed learning, learning motivation is essential and regardless of the results or effectiveness of learning, the respondents are still like to learn.
2. The students' level of academic achievement is *B+ Distinction* means that the students are performing well and able to understand the lesson well.
3. Since there was no significant relationship between students' level of self-directed learning and level of academic achievement, it is understandable that the level of self-directed learning doesn't affect the level of academic achievement. However, SDL provide access to a variety of abilities and skills that they may utilize to become greater learners.

In the light of the aforementioned findings and conclusions of this study; the following recommendations were offered:

1. The researchers recommend especially to the teachers because it will provide them with information about the effects of self-directed learning on academic achievement among students. It can also serve as a foundation for improving their teaching practices.

2. These researches also recommend to the UMPC school administrators for them to provide comments and recommendations to instructors in order to assist them in selecting the optimal strategy for promoting successful learning.
3. Despite of being already exposed to self-directed learning practice the students should continue practicing self-directed learning in order to know if where they are best and the needs of improvement while doing SDL. Moreover, in order to maintain having good grades students should continue to find ways on how to hone their learning and continue to practice their preferred learning style.
4. Since the study confirmed that there is no significant relationship between self-directed learning and academic achievement. This research will be utilized as a starting point for future researchers; they may use and develop this research. Future researchers can use other research designs to verify the result of this study and include other factors. The inclusion of other factors can play a significant role in evaluating the relationship of self-directed learning and academic achievement. Therefore, further study is required to clearly understand the true mechanisms between these two variables.

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